

Mozambique Geospatial Clean Cooking Access Modelling Using OnStove

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- Keywords

OnStove, GHG emissions, Benefits, Fuel cost, Time saved

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Executive Summary:

Access to clean cooking remains a critical challenge in Mozambique, where a significant portion (92%) of the population relies on traditional biomass fuels, contributing to adverse health and environmental impacts. During the training, the OnStove geospatial modelling tool was applied to compare cooking solutions, including improved cookstoves, LPG, electricity, and biogas, based on their costs, health benefits, and emissions in different geographic contexts.

The results presented are aligned with the Mozambican National Transition Strategy and National Energy Compact under SDG 7.

- Key Findings

- Based on policy data, such as the energy transition strategy, mission 300 compact, maximum benefits technology indicates: LPG, charcoal ICS and electricity stoves emerged as the maximum benefits and scalable solutions for the country, where electricity dominates for medium-high income households.
- Health and emission benefits: Charcoal has the highest net positive impact due to being more accessible or easier to scale in short term.

LPG has net impact offering stronger health or environmental benefits.

While electricity has large benefits is held back by significant barriers as cost or infrastructure limitations.

- Recommendations

Charcoal ICS

- Scale up distribution of improved cook stoves in areas with strong charcoal dependency
- Offer subsidies or micro-financing to make charcoal ICS more affordable
- Invest in public awareness campaigns about fuel efficiency and health benefits

LPG

- Improve supply chain infrastructure for LPG
- Subsidize initial LPG kits (stoves+cylinder) for low income households
- Implement safety education programs to build consumer confidence

Electricity

- Invest in grid reliability and affordability of electricity
- Promote energy-efficient electric cooking appliances

1. Introduction:

The purpose of this report is to support the application of the OnStove geospatial modelling tool to evaluate the net benefits of clean cooking solutions in Mozambique. The study aims to provide evidence-based insights into the cost-effectiveness and spatial distribution of various cooking technologies to inform policy and planning.

The scope of the work includes the collection, integration, and analysis of spatial, techno and socio-economic data to model and get maximum benefits of these technologies across the country. This includes both urban and rural contexts, considering energy access gaps, fuel availability, environmental impacts, and socio-economic conditions. The model outputs are intended to support national planning efforts under SDG 7, the Energy Transition Strategy and National Energy Compact (M300).

Main Objective:

- To select the stove with the highest net-benefit in each settlement in terms of Emission reduction, Time saved and Mortality reduction, based on several policy documents.

Specific Aims:

- To map and analyse the spatial distribution of clean cooking technology costs and benefits using OnStove.
- To integrate geospatial, demographic, techno and socio-economic data for modelling of cooking energy transitions.
- To generate actionable insights that support the Government of Mozambique in planning and implementing clean cooking interventions.

2. Methodology:

The modelling was done using OnStove, a geospatial clean cooking tool, to determine the net-benefit of cooking with different stoves across an area and support decision makers on clean cooking strategies across the Energy Transition Strategy, Compact, NDC. For Modelling was considered GIS data, techno-economic data and socio-economic data.

Socio-Economic Data

Assumptions:

Start year – 2030

End year – 2030

Population start year – 38744414

Population end year – 38744414

Urban start year - 35.8%

Urban end year - 35.8%

Elec_rate – 66.6 %

rural_elec_rate – 7%

urban_elec_rate – 91%

Fnr – 34

Rural_HHsize - 4.5

Urban_HHsize – 4.7

Meals_per_day – 3 meals

Wage – 125 USD/month

Techno-economic data

Assumptions:

Investment cost of stove

Electric – 10 USD

LPG – 20 USD

Tradition charcoal – 7.82 USD

Charcoal ICS – 12.51 USD

Fuel cost

Electric – 0.13 USD/kWh (tariff), 0.1 USD/kWh (Generation)

LPG – 1.35 USD/kg

Tradition charcoal – 0.47 USD/kg

Charcoal ICS – 0.47 USD/kg

Time_of_cooking – 1.5h (average)

Installed capacity

Hydro – 2.195 MW

Thermal –

Natural gas – 455.64 MW

Diesel – 82.10 MW

Solar – 99.24 MW

Charcoal – 56 MW

These parameters provide a comprehensive basis for running various clean cooking scenarios, enabling an evaluation of the benefits of adoption of clean cooking solutions focusing on enhancing communities' quality of life, cutting harmful emissions, lowering mortality and morbidity rates and reaching 2030 access goals.

The population data is important for indicating where the people live, while fuel sources locations allow to know which sources could be a solution for cooking purposes for the community in certain areas.

3. Results:

The transition to clean cooking is not just about technology and infrastructure; it is also about people, culture, and daily habits.

Improved cookstoves balance traditional habits with health benefits for households unable to afford alternative cooking methods.

Electricity is available in urban areas where the infrastructure supports it. This represents a future-forward possibility.

Over 8,000 deaths could be avoided each year from reduced indoor air pollution.

Health savings of 340 million USD annually, primarily due to reduced healthcare costs from respiratory illness.

Crucially, households could save over 1 hour of cooking time per day, which could be redirected for education, income generation, or other productive activities (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Maximum net-benefit cooking technology

Stove share

Charcoal ICS, though not the cleanest option, can serve as an effective transitional technology due to its availability and lower cost. On the other hand, LPG and electricity offer cleaner benefits but face significant barriers such as cost and lack of grid or off-grid connections (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Stove share

Benefits vs costs

Small negative contribution of the charcoal ICS from several factors, such as low income, source availability.

Large positive contributions suggest moderate benefits across several dimensions, such as efficiency, cost savings and environmental impact.

Moderate negative contribution of LPG in the environmental impact analysis. Strong positive contribution to the financial performance that indicates a positive impact.

The largest negative contribution of electricity among the three options indicates significant initial barriers, such as cost and infrastructure. However, the net benefit is still positive.

In summary, while charcoal ICS are cost-effective and readily available, LPG offers drawbacks; efforts should be made to provide cylinders and stoves at an affordable price, special in rural areas. Electricity remains the cleanest option but faces significant barriers such as infrastructure cost or reliability despite its clean benefits (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Investment cost

Relative wealth index

Households in areas with medium to high incomes and where there is energy infrastructures, electricity predominates, particularly in large urban centres.

However, in these same areas, some people use all three types of energy sources for cooking purposes, which indicates a gradual transition towards more diverse energy usage.

In areas with low-income households, improved cookstoves and LPG predominate, aligning with the master plan to increase LPG usage nationwide (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Relative wealth index

Maximum net benefits

For an effective transition, areas with fewer benefits will need financial support to improve health and environmental outcomes. In contrast, large urban centers which already have robust clean infrastructure will have greater benefits with minimal additional investment (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Maximum net benefits

4. Discussion:

The use of charcoal ICS contributes to reducing the pressure on forests by reducing the amount of coal used for cooking by up to 50 per cent. Although it is not a clean source, in the scenario presented, the use of charcoal ICS appears as a transitional technology towards cleaner energy solutions when compared to the current situation.

Leverage Charcoal ICS for short- to medium-term gains because it provides the highest net positive impact with relatively low barriers. Scaling up the distribution of improved charcoal stoves and offering subsidies or microfinancing could provide a roadmap for action.

For the LPG, expand access in urban and peri-urban areas by improving supply chain infrastructure, subsidizing initial kits and implementing safety education programs because it has a strong positive contribution, particularly to health and emissions.

These actions can gradually reduce the use of traditional biomass, improve health, and decrease deaths in rural.

In rural areas, charcoal ICS might be most feasible, in peri-urban zones LPG offers a good middle ground, in urban centers with strong grids, electricity can be prioritized.

By addressing these varied needs through targeted investment and policies, we can ensure that all communities benefit from safe, reliable and sustainable cooking solutions.

Challenges

The lack of specific legal framework and guidelines in the country for clean cooking is a major gap.

However, it's important to understand how the model works, including its underlying assumptions and limitations and the results it generates, which is crucial for informed decisions.

5. Conclusion:

OnSove relies on a combination of techno-economic data, socio-economic data and geospatial data to model clean cooking access to help understand the impact/ benefits of different clean cooking solutions on health, environment, and time saved on fuel collection.

The model highlights significant disparities between urban and rural areas in access to clean cooking solutions. Urban populations generally benefit from better infrastructure and access to modern fuels, while rural communities face persistent barriers such as limited affordability, supply chain constraints, and traditional cooking practices.

The insights from the model can inform policy decisions and investment strategies aimed at accelerating the transition to clean cooking in Mozambique.

- Recommendations

It is important to respect people's choice of cooking methods. Policies/strategic plans should be defined to guide the use of clean cooking solutions, as the benefits are significant in many ways, such as health and environmental benefits.

The diversification of affordable cooking technologies should be emphasised to ensure that people can choose and can contribute to achieving the universal goals of access to clean cooking solutions.

To successfully implement clean cooking to mobilize finance and public-private partnerships. The scale-up of clean cooking requires co-investment from governments, donors, and the private sector.

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